

Appendix – Supplementary Material 3

Abbreviation	Interviewee	Interview Repository Link
Bru	Claude Bruderlein	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18986945
Cap	Leonardo Caporarello	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974075
Con	Eugenia da Conceição Heldt	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974387
Har	Thibaud Harrois	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974402
Mon	Angelo Monoriti	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974519
Ran	Yadvinder Rana	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974533
Fer	Stéphanie Ferland	On request
Goe	Anne Marie Goetz	On request
Lid	Kristoffer Lidén	On request
Mur	Valon Murtezaj	On request
Ros	Valérie Rosoux	On request
Kal	Eleni Kalafati	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974551
Man	Ida Manton	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974562
RG	Mark Young	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974568
Vla	Anastasiia Vlasenko	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974577
Hem	John Hemery	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18974447
Vas	Dragos-Cristian Vasilescu	On request
Wae	Roar T. Waegger	On request
Smo	Remi Smolinski	On request